

ANALYSIS OF THE DRIVING FACTORS AND IMPACTS OF EARLY MARRIAGE IN MANTIKULORE SUB-DISTRICT PALU CITY

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11634936](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11634936)

Abstract

This research highlights the seriousness of early marriage issues in Indonesia, showing that 8.02% of Indonesian women married before the age of 18 in 2022, with Central Sulawesi ranking fifth at 12.65%. Mantikulore District has experienced fluctuating data over the past three years from 2021 to 2023. A qualitative study with a phenomenological design was used to analyze predisposing factors, enabling factors, reinforcing factors, social context, the impact of early marriage, and strategies of women involved in early marriage in Mantikulore District, Palu City. Data for this research were collected through interviews involving 7 women who were involved in early marriage, 7 husbands, 7 parents who played significant roles, and 1 religious affairs office (KUA) officer in Mantikulore considered relevant to the research objectives. The results of the study indicate that early marriage is triggered by the community's lack of knowledge about its negative impacts and limited access to information related to early marriage, which leads to pregnancy outside of marriage. Economic factors also play an important role in the decision to marry early. The impact of early marriage is felt as stress due to new responsibilities and roles within the household. To cope with this impact, women involved in early marriage focus on emotional support. This research concludes that early marriage in Mantikulore District is triggered by several factors, including lack of knowledge, limited access to information, economic pressure, and pregnancy outside of marriage. The experienced impacts include stress due to new responsibilities that are not aligned with the maturity needed to handle household issues. To address this, cross-sectoral collaboration is needed by maximizing adolescent health centers (posyandu remaja) to increase community understanding and address early marriage issues.

Keywords: Predisposing Factors, Enabling Factors, Early Marriage, Impact of Early Marriage.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of early marriage in Indonesia is a significant problem, as indicated by 2018 statistics which recorded that 11.21% of women in Indonesia married before reaching the age of 18. This data places Indonesia in eighth place in the country with the highest rate of early marriage in the world ¹

In the Revision of Law No. 16 of 2019 concerning Marriage, improvements were made by raising the minimum age limit for marriage for women from 16 years to 19 years. This change also applies to the minimum age limit for marriage for men. The aim of this modification is to improve the quality of marital relations, increase the quality of offspring, reduce birth rates, and reduce maternal and child mortality rates ².

Early marriage carries risks, including increased mortality rates, mental inability to cope with marriage, and failure in the relationship. In addition, early marriage can accelerate population growth because women of childbearing age tend to have more children. The average age of marriage may reflect the socio-economic situation of an area, and an increase in the number of young couples getting married may indicate inadequate socio-economic conditions ³.

Many unemployed women and men may choose to get married as a pastime, in the hope that good luck will come after marriage. In addition, early marriage has a significant psychological impact, where couples may not be mentally prepared to face changing roles and overcome problems in the marital relationship. This can lead to regrets due to missed school and teenage years ⁴.

Based on data collected by the Central Statistics Agency in 2022, early marriage was recorded as occurring in almost all regions in Indonesia. The highest rates of early marriage were identified in several regions, such as NTB with a percentage of 16.23%, Central Kalimantan 14.72%, Gorontalo 13.65%, West Kalimantan 12.84%, and Central Sulawesi 12.65%. Central Sulawesi is ranked fifth at the national level in terms of the number of early marriages, after West Kalimantan. Data shows that the number of early marriages in Central Sulawesi has fluctuated in the last three years. In 2020, the percentage of early marriages reached 14.89%, then decreased to 12.51% in 2021, and increased again to 12.65% in 2022 ⁵.

Palu City, as the capital of Central Sulawesi Province, faces similar challenges related to early marriage. Data from the Palu City Religious Court shows fluctuations in requests for marriage dispensations. In 2020, there were 60 cases of requests for dispensation, then decreased to 37 cases in 2021, and increased again to 42 cases in 2022. The problem of early marriage which is rampant in Palu City also has an impact on the high number of first pregnancies at very young ages. young. Girls aged 10-14 years have a five times higher risk of dying during pregnancy or childbirth compared to the 20-24 year age group. Meanwhile, this risk doubles in the 15-19 year age group. However, there is still a long way to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) target, especially in achieving the elimination of the practice of early marriage or the target of zero early marriage by 2030. Several Religious Affairs Offices (KUA) in Palu City stated that cases of early marriage in several regions experienced a significant decline, while in other places cases increased. This change is influenced by the perceptions and roles of parents in responding to early marriage ⁶.

Based on data from the Palu City Religious Court, there has been an increase in cases of early marriage over the last three years, with 17 cases in 2020, a decrease to 10 cases in 2021, and again increasing to 26 cases in 2022. As of May 2023, there were 16 requests for marriage dispensation, shows the potential for further improvement. Factors such as level of knowledge, economic conditions, culture, access to information, and family support influence this increase.

Meanwhile, a comparison of several Religious Affairs Offices (KUA) in Palu City shows variations. Mantikulore District experienced an increase in cases of early marriage, from 14 cases in 2021 to 20 cases in 2022, and in the January-October 2023 period there were 15 cases. This does not rule out the possibility of the number of children continuing to increase until the end of the year. On the other hand, West Palu District KUA and South Palu District KUA experienced a significant decline over the last three years. West Palu District KUA, from 27 cases in 2019, fell to 12 cases in 2020, and only 2 cases in 2021. Likewise, South Palu District KUA, from 13 cases in 2019, reduced to 8 cases in 2020, and only 3 cases in 2021. Interviews with Palu City Religious Court officials also show that although requests for marriage dispensations are increasing, not all of them are approved to prevent a significant increase in cases of early marriage in Palu City.

2. INFORMANT AND METHODS

The data collection process in this research began after obtaining approval from the Ethics Commission of the Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University. To maintain confidentiality and obtain informant consent, interviews were conducted after providing an initial explanation of the research objectives. Informants were given the opportunity to provide permission for voice recording during the interview and agreed to the informed consent provided by the researcher. The interviews began with open-ended questions according to a semi-structured interview guide. The question component involves aspects of the relationship between the context of early marriage, the roles of the parties involved, the coordination and informants carried out, and the mutual agreement formed. It is important to note that participant names used in research are not their real names, to maintain their confidentiality. In data analysis, qualitative content analysis techniques with a phenomenological approach were used. This approach helps in collecting, describing, describing and analyzing various conditions related to the driving factors and impacts of early marriage in Mantikulore District, Palu City. It is hoped that this method can contribute to increasing knowledge and controlling the impact of early marriage.

3. RESULT

3.1 Informant Characteristics

The selection of informants in this research used a purposive sampling method, which deliberately selected individuals with special characteristics that were in accordance with the research objectives. The selected informants are expected to have characteristics that can help researchers to investigate the context of early marriage in Mantikulore subdistrict. A total of 22 informants were involved in this research, divided into 7 women involved in early marriage, 7 husbands of these women, 7 parents who had a role in decision making regarding early marriage, and 1 officer from the Mantikulore Religious Affairs Office (KUA).

3.1.1 Predisposing Factors.

In the context of research on early marriage, predisposing factors refer to elements such as knowledge, level of education, and socio-cultural aspects that can project a person's likelihood of being involved in early marriage. This research considers predisposing factors as elements that influence an individual's tendency towards early marriage behavior, including their understanding of the concept, the level of education they have achieved, and the influence of social culture in the society in which they live.

3.1.1.1 Knowledge

The following is a summary of the results of interviews with female informants involved in early marriage to determine their knowledge regarding the context of early marriage:

“Early marriage is a marriage that occurs at a young age, such as junior high school students.... maybe when you are 17 years old you can get married... which causes early marriage because parents still believe in tradition, and also because of their desire. myself...in my opinion, as long as you are 17 years old, there are no further impacts” (PS 18 years old, women involved in early marriage)

” As far as I know, marriage occurs in children who are still small and are considered to be allowed to marry by their parents... 17 year olds are allowed to marry because they are considered teenagers... the reason for marrying young may be because of an arranged marriage carried out by their parents or because they like each other. So I want to get married... the most frequent impact is dropping out of school” (SA 18 years old female involved in early marriage)

The results of interviews with women involved in early marriage showed that the majority of informants faced difficulties in explaining the concept of early marriage. They tend to define early marriage only as marriage involving individuals in the child age category.

A number of informants also experienced difficulties in specifying age limits that were in accordance with applicable regulations in the context of early marriage, and included factors that could influence the practice of early marriage. However, they have an indirect understanding of some of the impacts associated with early marriage in the form of dropping out of school and their unpreparedness in taking care of the household..

Husbands also felt a lack of knowledge regarding the context of early marriage. This was clarified based on interview results which showed variations in their understanding. Several informants stated that early marriage is a marriage carried out at an age that does not meet the applicable terms and conditions. Meanwhile, some informants did not know the definition of early marriage.

When discussing the age limit for marriage, some of them have difficulty explaining the exact age limit for marriage. Regarding the factors causing early marriage, the majority of informants stated that parental encouragement and personal desires were the main drivers. They also mentioned the impact of early marriage, such as difficulties for the wife in taking care of her husband or being a burden for parents because they are not yet able to live independently. This was explained by several husband informants as follows :

“Like a child who is still at school but has been forced to marry by his parents....over 17 years seems like the right age to get married.... his parents who told him to get married or his close family who asked him to get married immediately.... It could be that because she was still young she was married off so she wasn't ready to take care of her husband” (AP 19 years old, husband of a woman involved in early marriage)

The inability to understand the context of early marriage felt by both women involved in early marriage and their husbands cannot be separated from the role of parental knowledge in understanding this concept. This research was also conducted together with parents who have an important role in making decisions about early marriage with the aim of clarifying their understanding of the concept of early marriage.

The results showed that some parents did not fully understand the concept of early marriage, with some stating that age marriage Early marriage is related to marriage at a very young age, such as elementary or middle school children. Some parents also believe that as long as their children reach adulthood, they can be married off, referring to ancient practices. Factors that influence early marriage include pregnancies outside of marriage and personal desires.

The recognized impact is the difficulty for these children to be independent in household life, which is explained through in-depth interviews as follows :

“Early marriage is a marriage that occurs when children are very young and not yet fit for marriage.... when he was 17 years old because he was considered mature.... their own desires, even if they come from their parents, definitely need their approval first... The impact is that you are immature in responding to situations and less independent” (SR 45, Parent)

“Children of elementary or middle school age whose parents force them to marry.... As far as I know, when I was 17 years old or had reached puberty... I already have to get married because I'm pregnant first, like it or not, I have to get married... The worst thing I have ever seen is getting divorced and going home to each other” (MS 49, Parent)

In-depth interviews with Mantikulore KUA officers as resource persons aimed to understand more deeply the concept of early marriage, the driving factors, and the impact of the practice of early marriage. The following are the results of interviews with Mantikulore KUA officers:

“Early age marriage is a marriage carried out under the age set by the government...yes, according to the regulations set, people can marry if both of them are 19 years old....which causes early age marriage most often because they are pregnant out of wedlock and have to get married but must attend a marriage dispensation hearing at the religious court first. If it is permitted then the marriage will be registered at the KUA... The impact of early marriage comes from many aspects, the most widespread here are divorce, domestic violence, and not being able to financially support a family that ultimately depends on parents. ” (KS 43 years old, KUA officer)

Interview findings show that early marriage is defined as marriage involving individuals under the age set by the government. The age limit for marriage according to government regulations is when both partners, both female and male, have reached the age of 19 years or more.

Factors that cause early marriage include the situation of pregnancy out of wedlock, which requires an application for marriage dispensation through a hearing in a religious court. If permission is given, the marriage can be carried out and recorded at the KUA.

The impacts that often occur involve the risk of divorce, domestic violence (KDRT), and economic inability to meet family needs. KUA officials stated that the KUA did not have the authority to grant permits for early marriage. Decisions regarding early marriage are left entirely to the religious courts, which have the authority to hold marriage isbat hearings for children who wish to marry.

After obtaining permission from the religious court, the marriage can be registered at the KUA. The following are the results of interviews with Mantikulore KUA officers :

“We at the KUA do not have the authority to allow early marriages, usually we leave it to the court to take part in the marriage dispensation hearing.” (KS 43 years old, KUA officer)

“First of all, when someone registers a marriage and is not old enough, we explain the marriage registration regulations, then if the marriage must take place, we make a letter of introduction to the religious court for a marriage isbat hearing. If it is approved, we will get a letter and we will immediately register it.” (KS 43 years old, KUA officer)

3.1.1.2 Level of Education

The results of interviews with women involved in early marriage showed that some informants stated that education level had the potential to influence the decision to marry at an early age, although it could not be used as an absolute benchmark. Even though some individuals are highly educated, they can still engage in the practice of early marriage in accordance with their personal decisions and religious values. Furthermore, the interview results also show the view that education level can influence a person's access to information regarding the impact of early marriage. Informants believe that individuals with a higher level of education tend to have greater knowledge about the negative impacts that may arise due to the practice of early marriage. Apart from that, some informants also stated that there were differences in knowledge between individuals with high and low education regarding early marriage. Although there are some who believe that this difference is not significant, there are also those who believe that each level of education makes a difference in understanding the issue of early marriage, because each level of education presents different knowledge. The following is an interview with women involved in early marriage to determine the influence of education level on the practice of early marriage:

“It could be because parents who have studied up to high school have different knowledge from parents who have graduated from middle school, let alone those who live in villages... Yes, it's definitely different, because I graduated from high school so I already know a few things about marriage, maybe those from the school below me don't know that... it depends, because usually information can be obtained from social media, some can also be obtained from school.” (PS 18 year old female involved in early marriage)

“Yes, maybe parents used to have incomplete education so they saw things in a different way regarding early marriage... yes, because this kind of knowledge is usually obtained while at school... no, because even though they have higher education, sometimes they still marry off their children. knows no age” (KH 18 years old, a woman involved in early marriage)

Husbands of women involved in early marriage expressed the same opinion, most informants acknowledged that the level of education has the potential to influence the decision to marry at an early age, because it can expand access to information. However, there is also a view that sometimes highly educated people tend to marry off their children quickly. Regarding understanding the impact of early marriage, the interview results show that there are differences of opinion. Some informants believe that individuals with higher education are more likely to be aware of the impacts and can consider these factors in decision making. Meanwhile, there are also those who argue that low-educated people do not always understand, they can even have knowledge, although not as much as highly educated individuals. Regarding differences in knowledge, some informants stated that there were differences that could be recognized because education could increase insight. However, there is also

a view that information is now easily accessible and does not always depend on the level of education.

The following are the results of interviews with the husbands of women involved in early marriage:

“It has an influence, maybe parents with higher levels of education get more information so they don't practice early marriage... I never got any information at school about the impact of early marriage... there is for sure, because school broadens our knowledge so if we teach it Regarding early marriage, their knowledge will definitely increase, if they are not taught, where will they get such information?”
(AP 19 years old, husband of a woman involved in an early marriage)

Their parents clarified that they agreed regarding the influence of education level on early marriage. The results show that the majority of parents think that the level of education plays a role in delaying early marriage, because those with higher education tend to have the critical ability to understand the impact of marriage. However, there is another view which states that uneducated people can also have knowledge through experience and information obtained outside formal education which was stated in an in-depth interview as follows:

“It is very influential because education brings an environment of friends, usually people who continue their education will focus more on going to school because the environment is like that, and people who do not continue their education usually prefer to get married because they are confused about what else to do next...it is influential, because of the good friendship environment highly educated will bring their thoughts too and they could share knowledge with each other about the impact of marriage.... There must be differences, because at each level of education the knowledge gained is different, so the knowledge a person has is also different, especially in important matters like this” **(IS 51 years old, Parent)**

In conclusion, the majority of informants agreed that education makes a difference in the level of knowledge regarding early marriage.

3.1.2 Enabling Factors

Based on the results of interviews with women involved in early marriage, discussing the availability of facilities and infrastructure that can help them to obtain information regarding early marriage, the results obtained, the majority of informants stated that although there are health facilities and infrastructure around them which are often used by residents, they never received information about early marriage from the health facility. On the other hand, some of them even get information about early marriage through social media platforms. The perspective that emerged from this interview shows that there are deficiencies in the delivery of information related to early marriage through health facilities. The following are the results of interviews with women involved in early marriage :

“Across there is the Talise health center.... I never got any information from the community health center, usually I only see on Instagram about early age marriages...a few weeks ago I saw a post passing by that in Palu City there were lots of early age marriages happening... if it works according to its function, yes, because many people go to the community health center for treatment, but I have never heard of information about early marriage.... I have never seen posters or the outreach that is carried out... in my opinion, it is not helpful because I feel like I don't

get any information about it. early marriage” (PS 18 years old, woman involved in early marriage)

“There is but it's a bit far from here about 500 meters.... never from that pustu...to be honest, I've never heard information about early marriage like that from the pustu...in my opinion, we don't think we should get information about early marriage there but this has never happened...when they convey it, it's usually directly when I visited there... no, maybe I didn't understand and never asked or there was no such information” (RM 20 years old, woman involved in early marriage)

The husbands of women involved in early marriages clarified this, that they were aware of the existence of health facilities around where they lived. Although these facilities function to serve the community's health needs, they never receive information about early marriage. They stated that this lack of knowledge may be due to their busy work schedule and infrequent visits to the community health center. Even before marriage, when they visited health facilities, they never received information regarding the context of marriage. The following are the results of interviews with the husbands of women involved in early marriage :

“The one near my house is a pustu, people often go there for treatment.... never, the early marriage that I explained earlier is only as far as I know.... I didn't get any information because I rarely went to the puskesmas or pustu because I was busy working... It works, people come to check their health, there are also doctors and nurses...not through both because I've never seen them...haven't helped, maybe one day it will be better” (AP 19 years old, husband of a woman involved in an early marriage)

It can be concluded based on the results of interviews with the two informants that the lack of knowledge regarding the concept of early marriage is also influenced by the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure to assist them in obtaining this information. And you need self-awareness in finding out information that has a positive impact on yourself

3.1.3 Impact of Early Marriage

Early marriage is often associated with higher physical, mental and social health risks for young couples. Women who marry at a young age are at higher risk of complications during pregnancy and childbirth, and are also more likely to experience domestic violence.

Based on the results of interviews with women involved in early marriage, the majority of informants stated that they experienced significant psychological impacts after marriage. They said they experienced stress due to fatigue in managing the household, difficulty in managing finances, lack of time to care for themselves like when they were girls, one of them even revealed that the factor that triggered the stress was because her husband was having an affair. Although most of them stated that their relationships with people around them were not disturbed, the frequency of meetings had become less frequent, but there was one of them who said that her relationship with her husband's family was not good because they were prohibited from seeing their children. Despite this, they were still able to maintain a good relationship. Emotional changes are also felt, where attention that was previously focused on oneself when they were young, now shifts to thinking about the goodness and integrity of the household. Even though one of them has to live separately from

her husband at the moment. The following are the results of interviews with female informants involved in early marriage :

"I sometimes feel stressed when I have to take care of my children and the household at the same time and since getting married I have become less able to take care of myself because I don't have time. In the end I feel like I'm not being taken care of even though before I got married I still had lots of time for that... because the house here is close by, I still I feel that the relationship with the neighbors is quite good because we usually sit around and talk in the afternoon... since getting married and having children, I sometimes get angry quickly, sometimes melt down quickly too." **(AG 19 years old, woman involved in early marriage)**

"Honestly, I'm really stressed, what's more, I have to take care of this myself and then I have a husband who likes to go out and play with his friends and doesn't want to share tasks at home... my relationship with my husband's family is not good because they don't allow me to meet my child... before marriage I was free and happier after marriage I felt very stressed and depressed because my husband was cheating on me which made me and my husband separate from home until now" **(PM 20 years old, woman involved in early marriage)**

Husbands of women involved in early marriages clarified that they also felt significant impacts after marriage. They experience high levels of stress, mainly caused by exhaustion in earning a living to meet their daily needs. Lack of support from the wife, who tends to get angry when she comes home from work, is also a contributing factor to the stress felt. Apart from that, they said that after getting married, they rarely met with friends because they focused on earning a living. Even though they occasionally steal time to relax, the frequency is decreasing. On average, they experience significant emotional changes after marriage, especially due to the large burden of responsibility as head of the household. However, when conducting interviews, the husbands did not reveal that their affair had caused them to separate from their current wife. The following are the results of interviews with the husbands of women involved in early marriage :

"Well, stress and the cause is if we have helped our wife but are still angry when we just get home from work, it feels wrong... My daily life apart from work is helping my wife at home because we have a laundry business with my in-laws, so I rarely see friends but sometimes I also go out with friends once in a while...there I have to work harder so I can support my family so they can at least eat" **(AP 18 years old, husband of a woman involved in an early marriage)**

"Because I'm tired of earning money from morning to night and don't get enough rest, I get emotional quickly if my wife asks a lot of questions that don't make sense... still like before, nothing gets worse, but being married means I can't spend time with my friends all the time. usually they are the ones who visit the house....not too different. At first they only thought about themselves. Now they have to think about their family first and they have to be responsible for providing for them." **(FD 19 years old, husband of a woman involved in an early marriage)**

In-depth interviews with Mantikulore KUA officers regarding the impact of early marriage yielded information that the impact involved problems of domestic violence, inability to support the family economically, and the most common is divorce. The following are the results of interviews with Mantikulore KUA officers :

“The impact of early marriage comes from many aspects, the most widespread here are divorce, domestic violence, and not being able to economically support a family that ultimately depends on parents.” (KS 43 years old, KUA officer)

Overall, it can be seen that the impact expressed by the informant is only in the form of a psychological impact, although the informant also feels an indirect economic impact. Bearing in mind that they have not yet achieved economic stability because some of them still live in their parents' house and are still assisted several times in fulfilling their economic needs.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Predisposing Factors

Predisposing factors refer to factors that can influence or project a person's likelihood of experiencing a condition or exhibiting a certain behavior. This predisposition component involves aspects such as genetics, social environment, culture, personal experiences, and other variables that play a role in shaping a person's predisposition towards a particular behavior or condition ⁷.

4.1.1 Knowledge

Early marriage is a behavior that is greatly impacted by knowledge since those who have a solid awareness of it can lessen its prevalence. Someone is likely to be more cautious when making judgments about an early marriage if they have a thorough grasp of the dangers and repercussions of it, including how it would affect their health, psychological well-being, and social factors ⁸.

Most of the respondents in this study, particularly the women who were married off young, as well as their husbands and parents, found it difficult to define early marriage. They usually hold the opinion that young marriages exclusively include those who are still in their childhood. Actually, their parents think that going through puberty signifies maturity and being ready for marriage. Most of them are ignorant about the legal age limit in Indonesia that applies to marriage. In addition, just a few of them have mentioned the negative effects of early marriage on their health and mental well-being, with the majority focusing solely on problems with household management. According to women who have early marriages with their spouses, their personal desires are what motivate them. However, their parents claimed that unintended pregnancies were the reason behind the early marriages. This demonstrates that there is a knowledge gap on the reasons for early marriage between the parents and younger generation getting married. Regarding early marriage, KUA representatives declared that they lacked the jurisdiction to provide marriage dispensations, or permits for early marriage. The religious court, which has the ability to hold marriage isbat hearings for youngsters who seek to marry, makes all the decisions about early marriage.

This study is consistent with that carried out in Baru Village, Kerinci Regency, by Arikhman ⁹. The study sheds light on the variables that affect early marriage. The study's findings showed that a sizable percentage of teenagers 48.5% married young. Low understanding about marriage is one of the factors that leads to early marriage in Baru Village, Kerinci Regency, where 61.2% of youth had little to no knowledge of early marriage. The results of this study also show that respondents with limited knowledge about early marriage are 4,286 times more likely to marry young than informants with good knowledge of the topic. These results highlight the strong

correlation that exists in these societies between the degree of knowledge and the propensity to enter into early marriage.

In a study conducted by Setyowati ¹⁰ in Trowulan District, Mojokerto Regency, to evaluate the impact of parental knowledge and attitudes towards adolescent reproductive health on the incidence of early marriage, the results of logistic regression analysis showed significant findings. The results of this analysis show that the variables of parental knowledge about adolescent reproductive health and parental attitudes towards adolescent health have a p-value <0.05, respectively 0.03 and 0.00. These findings prove that parents' knowledge and attitudes towards adolescent reproductive health have a significant influence on the incidence of early marriage in Trowulan District, Mojokerto Regency. The results of the logistic regression test explain that there is an inverse relationship between knowledge and attitudes and the incidence of early marriage. Parental knowledge about reproductive health and positive parental attitudes towards adolescent reproductive health have a negative impact on the incidence of early marriage, with B values of -1.077 and -3.024 respectively. Therefore, the higher the knowledge and the more positive the parents' attitude towards adolescent reproductive health, the lower the possibility of early marriage

The results of research done in Pamekasan Regency, which examined the impact of family support, culture, and knowledge on the incentive for early marriage, do not, however, align with the findings of this study. Using the correlation test, a significant value larger than 0.05, $p=0.410$, was discovered. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected. This demonstrates that knowledge and incentive for an early marriage do not significantly correlate. Weak correlation strength is indicated by a correlation coefficient value of -0.100. A negative number reflects the opposing relationship between knowledge and desire for an early marriage ¹¹.

4.1.2 Level of Education

A society's mentality and the process of making decisions are greatly influenced by education. The educational attainment of both parents and teenagers is a contributing factor to the phenomenon of early marriage. An individual's psychosocial maturity and capacity for problem-solving and sophisticated decision-making are both significantly impacted by their educational attainment. Young engagement in marriage is a common occurrence among adolescents with poor levels of education and awareness. In addition, as education is valued highly in the family setting, parents' education also plays a significant impact in the decisions that their children make. Thus, improving educational opportunities and standards can contribute to a decrease in the prevalence of early marriage ¹².

While some informants in the Mantikulore District have just completed junior high school, others have earned bachelor's or master's degrees, the average educational attainment of informants in the district is a high school diploma. While some women disagreed, the majority of women who participated in early marriage with their husbands said that their education level affected how they understood the practice. Some who disagree contend that ignorance is not always the same as lack of education, but it is a fact that education level affects one's capacity to comprehend information, particularly when it comes to early marriage. This viewpoint is consistent with their parents' beliefs, which hold that a person's social circle is influenced by their

education. Parents think that individuals who pursue higher education are more likely to be committed to a career in education, whereas those who drop out of school could instead choose to marry because they are unsure about what to do next. Even though parents have differing opinions, some of them are aware that information about early marriage is readily available from a variety of sources in this day and age. Conversations about how education affects one's understanding of early marriage are pertinent and demonstrate the disparities in perspectives among different generations and individuals.

These results align with studies that describe the dynamics of early marriage. According to this study, young teens with low levels of education are 4.259 times more likely than young teenagers with high levels of education to get married young. Compared to their peers with lower education levels, adolescents with higher education levels are less likely to get married young. One of the variables that affects how someone responds to issues, takes decisions, and matures psychosocially is their degree of schooling ¹³.

Not only should children's education be taken into account, but parents' educational attainment also has a significant influence in the practice of early marriage. Because education for children is prioritized above all else in the family setting, parental education has a significant impact on how children make decisions. This has been covered in a journal article about Indonesia's issue with early marriage. The publication highlights the fact that parents' knowledge, which is correlated with their educational attainment, has a crucial impact in the continuation of early marriage. Delaying the age of early marriage is largely the responsibility of parents. When making judgments for marriage at a young age, parents play a critical role since these choices are intimately tied to the dynamics of the connection between parents and children, including the impact of the child's peer group ¹².

This contrasts with the findings of a study by Adam ¹³ which discovered that only a small percentage of respondents (18%) with an elementary school (SD) education got married young. On the other hand, early marriage was not a factor for the majority of responders (65%) with elementary school (SD) education. A p-value of 0.565 ($p > 0.05$) indicates statistically that there is no significant correlation between an adolescent's educational attainment and early marriage ¹⁴.

4.2 Enabling Factor

The Mantikulore District environment's infrastructure and facilities are the primary enabling factor highlighted in this study. These infrastructure and facilities serve the community's need for knowledge and information around early marriage. This availability is intended to assist in lowering the Mantikulore District's early marriage rate ¹².

In the Mantikulore District, women who were involved in early marriage reported that they had never received counseling on the subject. Despite the fact that their neighborhood has health services, including community health centers and supportive community health centers, they are not aware of any youth posyandu that can offer information on early marriage and reproductive health. They also acknowledged that, with reference to the custom of early marriage in particular, they were ignorant of the existence of groups or establishments that defend women and children. It is challenging for them to obtain information from these establishments. This is a result of either their own ignorance or the government's lack of effort. The ladies claimed

that, while it doesn't always happen frequently, social media sites are where they typically find information about early marriage. They claimed to have seen such material, although it was frequently contradictory. From this comment, it can be inferred that they were unaware that the community health center had information on early marriage.

In the framework of health development, Youth Posyandu is anticipated to evolve into a type of Community Resource Health Effort (UKBM), which is started and managed by the community, particularly teenagers. The Youth Posyandu's primary goal is to empower the community, particularly the youth, and make health services easily accessible so that youth can lead healthier lives and enhance their general health. As a preventive and promotional measure, it is intended that Youth Posyandu's presence in the community will assist teenagers in developing an earlier understanding of reproductive health. This is an attempt to keep youngsters from engaging in free association. The promotive and preventive aspects of Posyandu's adolescent health services include things like Healthy Living Skills Education (PKHS), information on adolescent reproductive health, mental health services, drug abuse prevention, nutritional considerations, physical activity, and efforts to stop violence against teenagers. In this sense, the Youth Posyandu turns into a crucial platform that promotes teens' potential growth and comprehension of healthy lifestyles and constructive conduct in addition to offering physical health services ¹⁵.

Support for this statement can be found in the latest research conducted in Sindangman Village, Serang Regency, Banten Province in 2023. The research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of Youth Posyandu in increasing knowledge of adolescent reproductive health at Posrem Genius Sindangman Village. The results of the Wilcoxon test analysis showed a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that there was a significant difference between adolescent reproductive health knowledge before and after participating in Youth Posyandu activities. Therefore, it can be concluded that the Youth Posyandu in Sindangman Village has proven effective in increasing knowledge of adolescent reproductive health ¹⁶.

Research conducted by Aseri [17], which explored the role of the family and social environment in preventing early marriage in South Banjarmasin District, highlighted that collaboration with non-governmental organizations is an effective strategy for overcoming the issue of early marriage. Through outreach campaigns that provide education to the public about the dangers of early marriage, it can help increase their awareness and understanding of the negative impacts of marriage at a young age. Additionally, this campaign has the potential to change social norms that support early marriage and create a more supportive environment for young people to focus on education and personal development before considering marriage ¹⁷.

4.3 Impact of Early Marriage

Early marriage is often associated with higher health risks, both physical, mental and social for the young couples involved. Women who marry at a young age are at high risk of experiencing complications during pregnancy and childbirth. Apart from that, they are also more vulnerable to situations of domestic violence. This condition shows that early marriage can have a serious impact on well-being and health, both physical and psychological, especially for women who experience the marriage process at very early stages of development ⁶.

People in Mantikulore District have psychological effects from marriage, such as elevated stress levels brought on by the heavy load of housework, challenges with money management, and less time for self-care compared to their childhood. Some even went so far as to claim that their spouses' extramarital activities were the reason for their stress. The majority of informants acknowledged that they were no longer meeting with other people as frequently, even if they claimed that their ties with others around them had not been entirely destroyed. Additionally, others mentioned that their relationships with their husbands' family deteriorated, particularly when they were kept from seeing their kids. The majority of them are nevertheless able to keep up positive relationships in spite of this. The effects of an early marriage are also felt by the spouse, particularly in the form of elevated stress levels. This is brought on by exhaustion from working to support oneself. Stress is exacerbated by the wife's lack of support, as she often becomes irate after returning from work. Husbands also mentioned that because they were concentrating on making a living, they seldom ever met with friends after getting married. Even though they do occasionally snoop on people's downtime, it's becoming less often. After marriage, they typically go through major emotional shifts, mostly as a result of the heavy duty of becoming the head of the household.

According to the study, couples that marry young may experience negative effects including frequent conflicts or disagreements. Many things contribute to this argument, including the husband's need for fun, strong emotions, disagreements, and incompatibility from their early marriage. It might be challenging for some husbands to effectively perform their position as the household priest, which makes it challenging for them to provide good guidance to their partners. Selfish behaviors in day-to-day living and in search of meaning in life can also lead to conflict. Because of the selfish actions of one or both partners, many couples argue. This has the potential to seriously weaken the marriage bond and lead to arguments and conflicts that could endanger the union instead of bringing about harmony. Lack of knowledge and expertise in handling domestic issues is another element contributing to this conflict ¹³.

This study supports prior research's findings that 46.1% of participants reported stress levels that were within a normal range. Up to 29% of respondents reported feeling mildly stressed, followed by 15.3% who felt moderately stressed, 8.6% who felt severely stressed, and 1% who felt extremely stressed. According to the research's conclusions, there is a considerable psychological risk that those who marry young would experience psychological problems ¹⁸.

The psychological effects of early marriage under the framework of Islamic law have been studied, and the findings indicate that these effects are not uniform. Symptoms of unrestrained emotions, a lack of awareness of oneself as a wife, and a lack of grasp of the science of marriage are a few of these effects. These results give a general summary of the psychological risks that young marriage poses to children. Uncontrolled emotion symptoms may be an indication of emotional immaturity, which can have an impact on a child's mental health and psychological stability. Aside from that, youngsters are not yet quite ready to take on the duties and obligations of marriage if their wives lack knowledge and self-awareness ¹⁹.

The Mantikulore District's norm of early marriage has an implicit economic impact because it causes people to continue living at their parents' house while having jobs. Despite being married, they frequently continue rely on their parents for financial

support. Upon closer inspection, you'll notice that a few of them have failed to attain financial security while providing for their families...

According to a study, getting married young frequently starts a new cycle of poverty. Teenagers between the ages of 15 and 16 frequently lack the necessary financial maturity or, as a result of their inadequate education, do not have a respectable employment. Married children therefore continue to be a burden for the family, particularly for the husband or other male parent. Parents are left with a double burden as a result, having to support both their growing family and their own. Because of the propensity of this circumstance to recur from generation to generation, structural poverty develops²⁰.

5. CONCLUSION

- a. Predisposing factors for early marriage in Mantikulore District, Palu City, indicate that a large number of people marry because they engage in premarital sex that results in pregnancy, demonstrating the public's lack of understanding of child marriage and its effects, particularly with regard to the age limits for marriage.
- b. The Mantikulore District of Palu City's study on the elements that facilitate early marriage reveals that a contributing reason to the practice of early marriage is the community's lack of knowledge. Information about early marriage is not supported by the infrastructure and facilities in the area. There is a need to make information more accessible to the general people..
- c. In Mantikulore District, Palu City, the effects of early marriage include perplexity and worry over new obligations as a husband or wife, as well as lack of preparation for managing a home. Social relationships also change, and in certain circumstances, marital infidelity leads to a move away from one another.

Suggestion

Palu City's Mantikulore District has to work together across sectors to end the trend of early marriage. In the contemporary digital era, it is crucial to run programs or campaigns using easily accessible social media to raise public knowledge of early marriage, particularly about the age limit for marriage set by statutory regulations and the effects it produces. Reviewing the infrastructure and resources that encourage early marriage, such as youth posyandu, is also necessary. Community health center cadres should be given more authority to counsel adolescents and raise their awareness of reproductive health issues.

Use of AI tools declaration

The authors declare they have not used Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in the creation of this article.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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